

Do Personal Financial Practices Influence Happiness: A Cross-Sectional Analysis

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Abstract

Several studies emphasize the importance of personal financial practices in shaping the peoples' financial planning, investment behavior, and spending decisions. However, relatively few studies have explicitly examined the relationship between personal financial practices and subjective well-being, particularly happiness. This paper aimed to determine the effect of personal financial practices on behavioral outcomes such as happiness. It employed a cross-sectional research design using correlation and regression analyses based on data gathered from 930 respondents in the Philippines. The findings indicate that personal financial practices are a significant determinant of subjective well-being, specifically happiness. Personal financial practices function as socio-economic assets that foster resilience, empowerment, and happiness. Thus, the study suggests that strengthening personal financial practices not only enhances financial stability but also contributes to broader life satisfaction and overall happiness.

Keywords: Financial well-being, financial behavior, financial education program

Introduction

Recent literature affirm that personal financial practices strongly influence financial behavior, economic resilience, and overall well-being. Researchers across diverse contexts have shown that financial knowledge and capability shape how individuals manage money, accumulate resources, and respond to financial shocks. Mireku et al. (2023), Dunn (2023), and Rehman and Mia (2024) have collectively demonstrated that individuals with solid financial skills tend to borrow more responsibly, save more consistently, and engage in disciplined long-term planning. Together, these findings converge to position personal financial practices as central mechanism that enhances financial stability and reducing vulnerability.

In addition, personal financial practices are widely recognized as a core driver of effective financial decision-making, enabling the creation, preservation, and accumulation of wealth. Conversely, inadequate personal financial practices are associated with suboptimal money management, over-indebtedness, and diminished long-term financial security. Effective financial knowledge, skills, and behaviors enable individuals to save systematically, adopt disciplined spending patterns, and invest strategically to achieve both immediate and future objectives. Personal financial practices therefore extend beyond knowledge acquisition to include the development of financial awareness, analytical skills, positive attitudes, and responsible behaviors required for informed decision-making. Empirical evidence indicates

that applying financial concepts in daily life improves individual well-being (Servon & Kaestner, 2008), enhances savings behavior, supports sustainable spending patterns, and enables long-term wealth creation (Brown & Graf, 2013). Foundational theories further reinforce these perspectives: the life-cycle theory emphasizes the importance of aligning financial planning with life goals and stable income generation (Modigliani & Brumberg, 1954), while intertemporal choice theory emphasizes that rational decisions made in the present can yield greater utility and satisfaction in the future (Berns et al., 2007).

Beyond traditional economic outcomes, emerging studies highlight the broader psychological benefits of sound personal financial practices, particularly their influence on subjective well-being. Research in China (Huang et al., 2024), Jordan (Salameh et al., 2022), and the United States (Lusardi et al., 2023) demonstrate that financial capability enhances psychological security, autonomy, and life satisfaction. Synthesizing these insights, Cai et al. (2025), Mathew et al. (2022), and Sajid et al. (2024) argue that personal financial practices shape not only economic conditions but also social and emotional well-being, indicating a multidimensional role of financial behavior in human development.

Despite the expanding research on financial capability and well-being, relatively few studies examine how personal financial practices influence subjective well-being, particularly happiness. Cacnio and Romarate (2024) suggest that improved personal financial practices can reduce financial stress and positively shape financial behaviors across the life cycle. However, the extent to which these benefits translate into greater life satisfaction remains underexplored. As Sarigul (2014) notes, personal financial practices can enhance well-being by enabling individuals to make better lifestyle choices and well-informed decisions, yet empirical evidence linking these practices to happiness remains limited.

This knowledge gap is particularly relevant today due to several emerging developments. First, contemporary frameworks on happiness now consider broader dimensions such as social trust, institutional integrity, autonomy, and

perceptions of corruption—domains potentially influenced by personal financial practices. Second, the rapid digitalization of finance in the Philippines, including mobile wallets, online credit, and micro-investment platforms, has transformed financial behavior while introducing new risks and opportunities. Third, the COVID-19 pandemic intensified financial vulnerability and reshaped patterns of saving, credit use, and spending, signaling the need to revisit established relationships between financial practices and non-financial aspects of life. These shifts highlight the importance of renewed empirical investigation.

Given these concerns, the main objective of this study is to examine how personal financial practices relate to subjective well-being, particularly happiness. Using cross-sectional data, the study seeks to offer a contemporary assessment of financial practice indicators, including income, credit, spending, savings, investments, and retirement planning, and investigates how these factors correspond to six key domains of happiness, namely: income or GDP per capita, perceptions of corruption, generosity, freedom to make life choices, healthy life expectancy, and social support.

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

This study is grounded in psychological and economic perspectives that collectively explain how personal financial practices influence individual happiness. Central to this framework is Subjective Well-Being (SWB) Theory, which proposes that happiness is derived from both cognitive judgments of life satisfaction and affective experiences linked to perceived autonomy, competence, and emotional equilibrium (Diener, 1984; Diener et al., 1999). This theory is relevant to financial-psychological trade-offs because it emphasizes the internal processes through which financial behaviors influence well-being. Personal financial practices, including saving, budgeting, controlled spending, and long-term planning, therefore become psychological resources that contribute to emotional stability and improved life satisfaction.

Complementing SWB Theory, Financial Well-Being (FWB) Theory elucidates how financial behaviors shape overall well-being through the development of financial control, confidence, and security (Xiao & Xin, 2022; West et al., 2021). According to this theory, the positive effects of financial practices on happiness operate not merely through increased income or asset accumulation but through reduced economic uncertainty and improved resilience against financial shocks. Behaviors such as disciplined credit use, consistent savings accumulation, and informed investment engagement enhance individuals' sense of preparedness and optimism about their financial futures. As a result, these practices strengthen perceived financial well-being, which subsequently contributes to broader subjective well-being.

Further reinforcing this psychological dimension is Psychological Security Theory, which asserts that individuals experience greater subjective well-being when they feel economically safe, safeguarded against economic risks, and confident about their long-term financial stability (Cai et al., 2025). Financial behaviors that generate future-oriented benefits—particularly investment planning and retirement preparation—foster psychological security by reducing anxiety and reinforcing a sense of readiness for potential financial challenges. These mechanisms help explain why individuals with stronger financial habits typically enjoy higher satisfaction across non-material aspects of well-being, including personal freedom, social connectedness, and perceived physical health.

While psychological theories anchor the core mechanisms of the financial-happiness relationship, two economic theories offer important complementary insights into the temporal structure of financial decision-making. Life-Cycle Theory (Modigliani & Brumberg, 1954) argues that individuals allocate resources strategically across different stages of life in order to stabilize consumption and achieve long-term financial security. It also suggests that individuals seek to optimize consumption and savings decisions over their lifetime to achieve financial stability and well-being (Ando & Modigliani, 1963). This suggests that effective management of income, credit, savings, and investments can reduce uncertainty and promote

long-term security, which contributes to higher satisfaction with life. Similarly, Intertemporal Choice Theory (Berns et al., 2007) highlights the rational trade-offs individuals make between present and future consumption. This theory underscores how future-oriented behaviors, including investment decisions and spending discipline, are informed by expectations of higher future utility. Together, these economic perspectives illuminate how present financial choices generate both economic benefits and psychological well-being over time.

By integrating these psychological and economic perspectives, the study conceptualizes personal financial practices as influencing happiness through intertwined pathways. Financial behaviors are not viewed merely as mechanisms for resource management but as processes that actively cultivate autonomy, competence, emotional security, and perceived control. This integrated understanding forms the basis for the study's hypotheses, proposing that individuals with stronger financial practices are more likely to experience higher subjective well-being—both directly, through the benefits of responsible financial behavior, and indirectly, through the mediating effects of financial confidence and psychological security.

Anchored on these theories, the study proposes that personal financial practices function as both an economic and psychological resource that can enhance individual happiness. These practices are operationalized across six dimensions: income, credit, spending, savings, investment, and retirement planning—which collectively reflect an individual's ability to earn, allocate, protect, and grow financial resources across the life span. These practices develop financial competence, reduce vulnerability to financial stress, and foster a sense of empowerment and control, which are central determinants of subjective well-being (Sajid et al., 2024; Rehman & Mia, 2024).

Within this framework, happiness is conceptualized as an individual's overall life satisfaction and positive affect, following the multidimensional approach of the World Happiness Report (Helliwell et al., 2024). It is measured across six domains: income or GDP per capita, perceptions of corruption, generosity, freedom to make life choices, healthy life

expectancy, and social support. These domains encompass both material and non-material aspects of well-being, recognizing that financial competence influences not only economic stability but also social connectedness, health, and perceived freedom (Trabelsi et al., 2023; Ma et al., 2022; Huang et al., 2024).

The framework hypothesizes a direct and positive relationship between personal financial practices and happiness, suggesting that individuals with stronger financial practices are more likely to experience higher levels of subjective well-being. Additionally, it recognizes a potential indirect pathway through financial well-being or financial confidence—a mediating mechanism that reflects increased confidence and reduced financial stress—that enhances satisfaction with one’s financial situation (Xiao & Xin, 2022; West et al., 2021). This mediating variable links the behavioral dimensions of personal financial practices and psychological components of happiness, indicating that financial practices improve happiness not merely by increasing income but by enhancing an individual’s sense of security, autonomy, and empowerment.

Figure 1 illustrates the hypothesized relationships among the study variables.

Personal financial practices, represented by six indicators, are posited to exert both direct and indirect positive effects on happiness, either independently or through the mediating influence of financial well-being.

Personal Financial Practices. Personal Financial Practices is conceptualized as a multidimensional latent construct representing the set of behaviors, skills, and decisions individuals employ to manage financial resources across the life cycle. While operationally measured through six dimensions—income, credit, spending, savings, investment, and retirement planning—the indicators are grouped within the latent construct in the conceptual diagram to avoid unnecessary detail and enhance clarity. These dimensions collectively reflect an individual’s capacity to earn, allocate, protect, and grow financial resources. Income captures earning ability and access to financial resources essential for consumption, debt servicing, and future planning (Cai et al., 2025; Huang et al., 2024). Credit encompasses awareness, accessibility, and responsible use of borrowing facilities, including understanding credit terms and repayment obligations to avoid over-indebtedness (Simonse et al., 2024). Spending reflects consumption behavior and budget

Figure 1
Conceptual Framework

discipline that balance present needs with future security (Mathew et al., 2022). Savings relate to financial preparedness for emergencies and long-term objectives (Simonse et al., 2024). Investment reflects participation in wealth-building activities and the capacity to evaluate risks and returns (Yeo et al., 2024). Retirement planning includes the decisions individuals make to secure income in later life, such as participation in pension schemes and long-term savings mechanisms (Adee et al., 2024). These dimensions form a comprehensive understanding of Personal Financial Practices as an integrated financial behavior system.

Happiness. Happiness is framed as a latent construct representing subjective well-being, consistent with the multidimensional approach of the World Happiness Report. Happiness is measured through six domains—GDP per capita, perceptions of corruption, generosity, freedom to make life choices, healthy life expectancy, and social support. GDP per capita serves as an indicator of material well-being and individuals' capacity to meet basic and aspirational needs (Cai et al., 2025; Huang et al., 2024). Perceptions of corruption reflect institutional trust and perceived fairness in governance, both of which influence life satisfaction (Ma et al., 2022; Salameh et al., 2022). Generosity captures prosocial behaviors such as giving and volunteerism that enhance personal fulfillment and social cohesion (Trabelsi et al., 2023). Freedom to make life choices reflects perceived autonomy in major life decisions and strongly relates to overall satisfaction (Trabelsi et al., 2023). Healthy life expectancy integrates health status and longevity, recognizing physical well-being as a central determinant of happiness (Salameh et al., 2022). Social support measures the perceived reliability of support networks, which consistently contribute to emotional resilience and subjective well-being (Trabelsi et al., 2023). Collectively, these domains present a comprehensive picture of happiness as a multidimensional construct encompassing economic, social, psychological, and health-related facets of well-being.

Methodology

This research employed a cross-sectional design using a descriptive survey to collect data from adult individuals residing in Baguio City, Philippines. A total of 930 respondents participated in the study in 2023. The study did not utilize a formal probability or non-probability sampling technique; instead, data were gathered through on-site survey administration. All individuals who met the inclusion criteria and were present in the survey locations during data collection were invited to participate, reflecting an availability-based recruitment process dependent on the respondents' presence and willingness to provide informed consent. Although this method does not constitute a structured sampling approach, representation was improved by conducting the survey across multiple locations, at different times of the day, and among diverse socio-economic settings within Baguio City. The resulting sample of 930 qualified adults exceeds the minimum requirement for cross-sectional regression analysis, thereby enhancing the robustness and reliability of the study's inferential results.

Questionnaire Development

The questionnaire used in this study was researcher-developed, but incorporated elements from established and validated instruments, making it a hybrid tool. The items measuring the six dimensions of personal financial practices (income, credit, spending, savings, investment, and retirement planning) were informed by existing frameworks in financial literacy and financial behavior literature. The measures of happiness were aligned with the six domains utilized in the World Happiness Report (Helliwell et al., 2024).

Validity and Reliability Test

Three experts validated the questionnaire, where the validity test using Aiken's V resulted in a coefficient of 94.16% indicating that the questionnaire is valid. A pilot study was also conducted using 30 questionnaires that were pre-tested. The Cronbach's alpha test values lie from

0 to 1, with a threshold of 0.7 and above being reliable. Therefore, it is expected that when items have Cronbach's alpha values of 0.7 and above, the item question will be taken for further analysis.

Normality Test

The study used the Shapiro-Wilk test to check whether a sample comes from a normally distributed population. The null hypothesis states that "the data are drawn from a normally distributed population." The study used 5% as the significance level. The results of the normality test as shown in Appendix A indicates the non-normality of the data.

Correlation Analysis

Due to the identified issues about normality, the study used the Spearman's Rank as a tool to determine the relationship of personal financial practices and happiness.

Regression Analysis

To determine the strength of association of the variables, the study further used multiple regression analysis, as the data is cross-sectional and involves a one-time period. To ensure the validity of the results, the study conducted various tests such as multicollinearity, adequacy, heteroscedasticity and autocorrelation. The multicollinearity test determines if the independent variables are not correlated, which could affect the coefficients and the p-value. To check for multicollinearity issues, the variance inflation factor (VIF) was used, wherein the benchmark for acceptability should be less than ten ($VIF \leq 10$). The test found no issues regarding the multicollinearity of the independent variables as shown in Appendix B.

The model of the study is prescribed as:

$$Y^g = \alpha + \beta_1 PFP'_1 + \varepsilon$$

Where Y^g represents the happiness index, where g represents the six key domains: income or gross domestic product per capita (GDP/C), corruption, generosity, freedom to make life

choices (Freedom), healthy life expectancy (Health), and social support (Social). The independent variables are the personal financial practices indicators, which include income, credit, spending, savings, investment, and retirement planning.

The Ramsey's RESET Specification Test was conducted to ensure that the regression models were correctly specified. Results indicate that the models for income (GDP per capita), corruption, generosity, freedom to make life choices (Freedom), and healthy life expectancy were adequately specified, while the social support model was not (Appendix D).

Further, White's test verified the assumption of homoscedasticity, ensuring constant variance of the error term. The income model met this assumption, while the models for corruption, generosity, freedom to make life choices, healthy life expectancy, and social support exhibited heteroscedasticity. To address this, heteroscedasticity-corrected corrected multiple-regression models were applied, enhancing the reliability of coefficient estimates and the accuracy of statistical inference (Astivia & Zumbo, 2019; Appendix F)

Results

Using correlation and regression analyses, the study assessed the strength, significance, and predictive effect of personal financial practices on happiness outcomes. Table 1 presents the correlations between personal financial practices and the indicators of happiness, while Table 2 reports the regression results showing the effects of personal financial practices on the indicators of happiness.

The results indicate a statistically significant positive relationship between personal financial practices and happiness ($\rho = 0.6802$, $p < 0.01$). In particular, the dimensions of personal financial practices—including income, credit management, spending (both short- and long-term), savings, investment, and retirement planning—exhibit significant positive correlations with key indicators of the happiness index. These indicators include perceptions of income or gross domestic product per capita (GDP/C), corruption, generosity, freedom to make

Table 1
Relationship of Personal Financial Practices and Happiness

	Correlation	GDP/C	Corruption	Generosity	Freedom	Health	Social	Happiness
Income	Coeff.	0.5430	0.3824	0.5374	0.4127	0.4933	0.1899	0.6309
	P-Val.	<0.01*	<0.01*	<0.01*	<0.01*	<0.01*	<0.01*	< 0.01*
Credit	Coeff.	0.3463	0.3304	0.3819	0.1472	0.3604	0.0164	0.4009
	P-Val.	<0.01*	<0.01*	<0.01*	<0.01*	<0.01*	0.6184	< 0.01*
Spending	Coeff.	0.4089	0.2006	0.4446	0.3625	0.3015	0.2621	0.4595
	P-Val.	<0.01*	<0.01*	<0.01*	<0.01*	<0.01*	<0.01*	< 0.01*
Savings	Coeff.	0.4967	0.3098	0.4703	0.3469	0.4856	0.1053	0.5432
	P-Val.	<0.01*	<0.01*	<0.01*	<0.01*	<0.01*	<0.01*	< 0.01*
Investment	Coeff.	0.4654	0.3458	0.4929	0.3383	0.4678	0.1051	0.5438
	P-Val.	<0.01*	<0.01*	<0.01*	<0.01*	<0.01*	<0.01*	< 0.01*
Retirement	Coeff.	0.5490	0.3556	0.5224	0.3358	0.5338	0.0742	0.5985
	P-Val.	<0.01*	<0.01*	<0.01*	<0.01*	<0.01*	0.024*	< 0.01*
Personal Financial Practices	Coeff.	0.6009	0.4195	0.6020	0.4097	0.5775	0.1391	0.6802
	P-Val.	< 0.01*	< 0.01*	< 0.01*	< 0.01*	< 0.01*	< 0.01*	< 0.01*

Table 2
The Effect of Personal Financial Practices on Happiness

	Regression	GDP/C	Corruption	Generosity	Freedom	Health	Social
Const	Coeff	0.5024	1.9089	1.0284	2.6191	2.5366	4.0899
	P-Val.	0.0465*	<0.01*	<0.01*	<0.01*	<0.01*	<0.01*
Income	Coeff.	0.3331	0.2191	0.1726	0.2756	0.1287	0.1924
	P-Val.	<0.01*	<0.01*	<0.01*	<0.01*	<0.0014*	<0.01*
Credit	Coeff.	-0.0577	0.1623	0.0309	-0.1491	0.0146	-0.0466
	P-Val.	0.1486	0.0004*	0.3360	<0.01*	0.6044	0.0957
Spending	Coeff.	0.1732	-0.0593	0.2233	0.2643	-0.0430	0.3294
	P-Val.	0.0016*	0.3140	<0.01*	<0.01*	0.3709	<0.01*
Savings	Coeff.	0.1241	0.0662	0.0385	-0.0083	0.1573	-0.1418
	P-Val.	0.0119*	0.2299	0.2883	0.8418	<0.0001*	<0.0002*
Investment	Coeff.	0.0602	0.1078	0.2147	0.1168	0.1227	0.03011
	P-Val.	0.1656	0.0303*	<0.01*	<0.0005*	<0.0007*	0.3318
Retirement	Coeff.	0.2306	0.0932	0.1311	0.0701	0.2048	-0.0323
	P-Val.	<0.01*	0.0283*	<0.01*	<0.0083*	<0.01*	0.1733

life choices (Freedom), healthy life expectancy (Health), and social support (Social). This means that individuals with higher levels of personal financial practices are more likely to experience greater well-being, as reflected across multiple social, economic, and psychological dimensions of happiness.

The results reveal that the dimensions of personal financial practices can significantly affect the individual's perception on happiness. Income positively affects all six dimensions of happiness: GDP per capita or income, corruption, generosity, freedom, health and social. Credit has significant positive association with corruption but a negative association with freedom, suggesting that credit use may increase financial burdens and reduce autonomy. Spending is positively linked with GDP per capita or income, generosity, freedom and social. Savings can significantly improve individual's perception on GDP per capita or income, health, and social. Investment has positive effects on corruption, generosity, freedom, and health. Finally, retirement planning demonstrates significant positive effect on GDP per capita, corruption, generosity, freedom, and health.

Discussion

The study aimed to determine if personal financial practices matter to individual's perception about happiness. The results reveal that the dimensions of personal financial practices can serve as drivers of happiness, as they contribute significantly to improvements in both economic and social well-being. The findings demonstrate that personal financial practices across six dimensions—income, credit, spending, savings, investment, and retirement planning—significantly contribute to the six domains of happiness. Individuals with higher levels of personal financial practices as reflected in their practices on income, credit, spending, savings, investing, and retirement planning; achieve greater happiness along perceptions of GDP per capita (income), corruption, generosity, freedom, health, and social support. Personal financial practices on income emerges as a factor that positively affects all dimensions of happiness while other components such as spending,

savings, investment, and retirement planning also significantly contribute to the overall socio-economic well-being of individuals. Meanwhile, credit practices reveals mixed effects whereas it manifests potential risks when financial obligations can undermine perceptions of freedom. The findings confirm the hypothesized relationship between personal financial practices and subjective well-being such as happiness. These findings reinforce the growing body of literature highlighting that personal financial practices are not only an economic resource but also a critical factor influencing psychological and social well-being (Xiao & Xin, 2022).

From a theoretical perspective, these results align with psychological and economic frameworks that explain the mechanisms underlying the financial–happiness relationship. Subjective Well-Being (SWB) Theory suggests that happiness derives from both cognitive judgments of life satisfaction and affective experiences linked to autonomy, competence, and emotional equilibrium (Diener, 1984; Diener et al., 1999). Personal financial practices, including saving, budgeting, controlled spending, and long-term planning, act as psychological resources that promote emotional stability and life satisfaction. Financial Well-Being (FWB) Theory further elucidates that these practices enhance overall well-being by fostering financial control, confidence, and security, reducing economic uncertainty, and improving resilience against financial shocks (Xiao & Xin, 2022; West et al., 2021). Similarly, Psychological Security Theory posits that behaviors generating future-oriented benefits – such as investment and retirement planning – enhance psychological security, reducing anxiety and supporting perceived readiness for potential financial challenges (Cai et al., 2025).

These psychological mechanisms complement economic perspectives, particularly Life-Cycle Theory and Intertemporal Choice Theory, which highlight how individuals strategically allocate resources across life stages to stabilize consumption, optimize savings, and make rational trade-offs between present and future consumption (Modigliani & Brumberg, 1954; Ando & Modigliani, 1963; Berns et al., 2007). Together, these frameworks demonstrate that effective financial management produces both

tangible economic benefits and intangible psychological gains over time, thereby reinforcing subjective well-being.

In the present study, income practices were found to have a positive effect on all dimensions of happiness, which highlights its benefit on the socio-economic aspects of individuals. Greater knowledge, skills and attitude enables individuals to generate income for themselves and allocate resources efficiently, reduce financial stress, and engage more fully in social life. This would foster satisfaction and optimism among individuals. These results corroborate the findings of Xia and Xin (2022) wherein financial knowledge predicts well-being outcomes more effectively than income alone.

Credit practices, however, presented more complex results. While positively associated with perceptions of corruption, it was negatively linked to freedom, suggesting that although access to credit may reflect institutional efficiency, excessive reliance on credit could undermine personal autonomy. This resonates with research showing that poor credit management increases debt stress, thereby constraining decision-making freedom and lowering life satisfaction (Lusardi et al., 2023).

Spending practices exhibited positive associations with income, generosity, freedom, and social support. This suggests that individuals who engage in deliberate spending behaviors are more likely to experience financial stability and contribute to social and communal well-being. Similarly, savings practices were significantly related to perceptions of income, health, and social support, highlighting the protective role of savings in improving resilience against financial shocks and strengthening perceptions of stability and security (Das, 2025).

Investment practices showed positive effects on perceptions of corruption, generosity, freedom, and health, implying that individuals with the capacity to make informed investment decisions may experience greater empowerment and institutional trust. Retirement planning practices also had broad positive effects on income perception, corruption, generosity, freedom, and health, pointing to the role of future-oriented financial behavior in fostering optimism and reducing uncertainty. These findings reinforce studies suggesting that financial confidence

and forward-looking behavior mediate the relationship between financial practices and well-being (West et al., 2021).

Overall, these results underscore that personal financial practices function as both economic and psychological resources. They cultivate autonomy, competence, emotional security, and perceived control, demonstrating that financial behavior shapes happiness not merely through increased income but through enhanced confidence, reduced stress, and greater preparedness for future challenges. This integrated understanding confirms the study's hypotheses, highlighting the direct and indirect pathways through which financial practices influence subjective well-being.

This study contributes to the growing empirical evidence that personal financial practices exert substantial influence on subjective well-being beyond income alone. The ability to make informed and responsible financial decisions reduces uncertainty, mitigates financial stress, and enhances confidence and optimism – elements that directly support subjective well-being. Personal financial practices should therefore be regarded as a multidimensional life skill with social, psychological, and economic implications. On the practical side, this points out to the importance of education programs to improve personal financial practices especially in income, credit, spending, savings, investment, and retirement planning, including the need for responsible credit use in order to mitigate debt-related stress.

Despite its contributions, the study has methodological considerations that influence the interpretation and generalizability of its findings. As the respondents were recruited through an availability-based approach rather than a formal sampling design, external validity is limited and caution should be exercised when extending the results beyond the study area. Nevertheless, replicability remains feasible because the procedures, inclusion criteria, and survey conditions were clearly defined and can be reproduced under similar contexts. Moreover, the large sample size and the collection of data from diverse locations and socio-economic settings strengthen the internal validity of the results and support the reliability of the inferential analyses.

Finally, the cross-sectional design does not allow for causal claims or an assessment of changes over time. Geographic and socio-cultural factors may also moderate the relationship between financial practices and happiness. Future research should consider longitudinal approaches, multi-site sampling, and examinations of mediating influences such as socio-cultural context. Additionally, integrating digital financial behavior – an increasingly important component of modern financial practices – may offer deeper insights into how evolving financial environments shape happiness and general well-being.

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Appendices

A. Normality Test

Variable	Coeff.	P-Value	Normality
Income	0.9672	<0.01*	Not normal
Credit	0.9665	<0.01*	Not normal
Spending	0.9207	<0.01*	Not normal
Savings	0.9484	<0.01*	Not normal
Investment	0.9644	<0.01*	Not normal
Retirement	0.9313	<0.01*	Not normal
GDP/Cap	0.9065	<0.01*	Not normal
Corruption	0.9559	<0.01*	Not normal
Generosity	0.9563	<0.01*	Not normal
Freedom	0.9114	<0.01*	Not normal
Health	0.9478	<0.01*	Not normal
Social	0.8472	<0.01*	Not normal

B. Multicollinearity Test

Variables	VIF
Income	2.373
Credit	1.729
Spending	1.625
Savings	2.322
Investment	2.247
Retirement	2.359

C. Linearity Test

Null Hypothesis: Relationship is linear

Model	Test Statistic	P-value	Interpretation
GDP per capita	11.7509	0.0678	Accept
Corruption	6.9941	0.3214	Accept
Generosity	33.1743	<0.01	Reject
Freedom	36.54	<0.01	Reject
Health	17.0154	<0.01	Reject
Social	34.6977	<0.01	Reject

D. Ramsey's Rest Specification Test

Null Hypothesis: Specification is adequate

Model	Test Statistic	P-value	Interpretation
GDP per capita	0.7155	0.4892	Accept
Corruption	2.9094	0.055	Accept
Generosity	0.0424	0.958	Accept
Freedom	1.7490	0.175	Accept
Health	2.2525	0.106	Accept
Social	3.0414	0.0483	Reject

E. Normality of Residual

Null Hypothesis: Error is normally distributed

Model	Test Statistic	P-value	Interpretation
GDP per capita	711.235	<0.01	Reject
Corruption	49.152	<0.01	Reject
Generosity	62.742	<0.01	Reject
Freedom	57.984	<0.01	Reject
Health	33.438	<0.01	Reject
Social	243.074	<0.01	Reject

F. Heteroscedasticity Test

Null Hypothesis: Heteroscedasticity not present

Model	Test Statistic	P-value	Interpretation
GDP per capita	19.564	0.8485	Accept
Corruption	83.2177	<0.01	Reject
Generosity	107.1914	<0.01	Reject
Freedom	183.8885	<0.01	Reject
Health	159.5533	<0.01	Reject
Social	153.088	<0.01	Reject